



Supplementary Figure S1. *V. cholerae* C6706 EI Tor wild type growth in LB, minimal 0.5% mucin (Sigma Type III porcine gastric mucin) (MMu), and minimal media with no added carbon source (M). Data represent the average and SEM for three independent biological replicates.